

Bethsaida Excavations Project: Coins from the 2001–2012 Seasons.

Gregory C. Jenks

School of Theology, Charles Sturt University
Co-Director, Bethsaida Excavations Project

gjenks@csu.edu.au

This report covers the 139 coins recovered at the Bethsaida excavations between 2001 and 2012.

2012	23 coins	2006	8 coins
2011	16 coins	2005	13 coins
2010	14 coins	2004	3 coins
2009	10 coins	2003	10 coins
2008	26 coins	2002	(no coins)
2007	11 coins	2001	5 coins

The detailed descriptions of these coins have been prepared under the direction of Donald T. Ariel from the Israel Antiquities Authority coin department, and seek to capture the data recorded in the index cards at IAA. It supplements the earlier reports by Ariel Kindler and Cecilia Meier:

Kindler 1999, “Coin Finds at Bethsaida Excavations.”

Kindler 2009, “Bethsaida Numismatic Survey.”

Meier 1995, “Appendix to Chapter 1.”

For descriptions of the 384 coins recovered in previous seasons, see the reports by Kindler (1999 and 2009) and Meier (1995). Future reports will include coins from subsequent seasons as well as revisions of the descriptions of the earlier coins.

When reading these descriptions please keep in mind that—after as much as 2,000 years (or more) in the ground—the coins from Bethsaida, which are mostly bronze coins, are rarely in good condition. Descriptions of the design are derived from the comparative literature and may not be well preserved on the specific coin. On the other hand, descriptions of the legends will indicate the extent to which any inscriptions are visible on the particular coin from Bethsaida.

Letters in inscriptions with underline indicate a letter that is not sufficiently clear for a confident reading. The proposal is conjectural to some extent.

[] *indicates text not visible but conjectural*

[...] *legend is visible but illegible*

| *indicates a line break on the coin*

— *indicates a gap between letters*

Cf. *indicates that the literature cited is not the same coin but a similar coin*

2012 Season (23 coins)

[01] 138727 | B11250 | L1149 | L59 | Area A South

Autonomous, Tyre, Bronze, 98/97 BCE–84/85 CE

Weight: 5.64 g
Diameter: 19 mm
Axis: 12
Obv design: Head of Tyche, r., wearing turreted crown, veil, and earring; behind, palm-branch; border of dots.
Rev legend: $\text{IEPA}\Sigma$ [ΑΣΥΛΟΥ]
Rev design: Galley, l., with prow terminating in volute, and aphlaston at stern; above, date, monogram; below, Phoen. inscr. (lamed tsade resh); border of dots.
Literature: Cf. *BMC Phoen*: 255, No 252

[02] 138728 | B23481 | L2230 | F58 | Area A West

Autonomous, Tyre, Bronze, 112/13 CE

Weight: 6.10 g
Diameter: 19 mm & 12 mm
Axis: 12
Obv design: Bust of Tyche, r., wearing turreted crown, veil, an earring; behind, palm-branch; border of dots.
Rev legend: HAC | $\text{IEPA}\Sigma$ | MHT [ΡΟΠΙΟ] | Δ [$\text{EW}\Sigma$]
Rev design: Galley, l., with prow terminating in volute, and aphlaston at stern; above, in four lines, date and inscr. (usually of the flan), Phoen. inscr. (lamed tsade resh); border of dots.
Literature: *BMC Phoen*: 262–63, No 315–17

[03] 138729 | B23508 | L2230 | F58 | Area A West

Mark Antony, Aka-Ptolemais, Bronze, 35/34 BCE

Weight: 7.59g
Diameter: 21 mm x 23 mm
Axis: 12
Obv design: Head of Mark Antony, r., bareheaded, enclosed in laurel-wreath.
Rev legend: ΠΤΟΛΕΜΑΙΕΩΝ – [ΤΟΥ ΚΑΙ] AI
[Cf. Kadman 1961: M^oA IE / IEPACACTYAOY ; RPC: in fields: IE and ΛΓ ; $\text{ΠΤΟΛΕΜΑΙΕΩΝ ΤΟΥ ΚΑΙ}$ (around); and Meshorer 1985: $\text{ΠΤΟΛΕΜΑΙΕΩΝ IEP KAI AΣΥΛΟΥ IE}$ ('of the people of Ptolemais, holy and city of asylum'), in field date ('year 3' = 43 BCE). IM 78.3517 has no sign of iota (I) or epsilon (E) and the ambiguous third letter could be the base of either rho (P) or upsilon (Y). The kappa (K) is clearly visible in this example.]
Rev design: Diademed bust of Cleopatra, r.; border of dots.
Literature: Cf. Kadman 1961: 106–7, No 74; *RPC* I: 659, No 4742; Meshorer 1985: 110, No 1 (=Israel Museum 78.3517)

[04] 138730 | B23479 | L2241 | G57 | Area A West

Hasmonean, Jerusalem, Bronze, 135–37 BCE

Weight: 1.15 g
Diameter: 13 mm
Axis: 12
Obv legend: η [...] | η [...] | צה [...]
Obv design: Paleo-Hebrew inscr. within wreath
Rev design: Double cornucopiae with pomegranite between

[05] 138731 | B23480 | L2241 | G57 | Area A West

Antoninus Pius, Rome, Silver, 145–161 CE

Weight: 2.76 g
Diameter: 18 mm
Axis: 12
Obv legend: [A] $\text{NTONINVS AVG PI} - \text{VS PP}$ [IMP II]
Rev design: $\text{COS} - \text{II}$ [II]
Literature: Cf. *CRE* IV: 75, No 520 (or 111, No 766 or 123, No 841)

[06] 138732 | B22533 | L2246 | F58 | Area A West

Caracalla, Tyre, Bronze, 198–217 CE

Weight: 11.78 g
Diameter: 26 mm
Axis: 6
Obv legend: IMP M AV[R A] - NTONINVS
Obv design: Bust of Caracalla, r., undraped, laureate
Rev legend: ACT[IA]
Rev design: Agonistic table supporting two prize-crowns; on either side of it, a palm-branch; below, murex-shell; above, ACTIA; in ex., ERACLIA; around, SEPTVRVSMETROCOLONIA
Literature: *BMC Phoen*: 271, No 379

[07] 138733 | B22558 | L2246 | F58 | Area A West

Hasmonean, Jerusalem, Bronze, 135–37 BCE

Weight: 1.60 g
Diameter: 13 mm
Obv legend: [...] | לַח[...] | [...] בַּי [...] | [...]
Obv design: Paleo-Hebrew inscr. within wreath

[08] 138734 | B22525 | L2247 | F58 | Area A West

Severus Alexander, Orthosia, Bronze, 221/222 CE

Weight: 9.18 g
Diameter: 24 mm
Axis: 1
Obv design: Head of Severus Alexander, r., inscr. AVKMAV
Rev legend: ΟΡΘΩ — [C] — [E] — ΩΝ
Rev design: Temple of Astarte with four columns, pediment, arch over central space, and doorways (with steps leading up to them) between columns on either side; in center, Astarte wearing kalathos and raising dress with l. hand, standing to front, her l. foot on half-figure of a river-god; she rests r. on standard, and is crowned by small Nike on column beside her; in ex., altar; around, from l. upwards inscr.; in ex., date (ΓΛ[Θ]).
Literature: Cf. *BMC Phoen*: 127, No 5

[09] 138735 | B22527 | L2247 | F58 | Area A West

Autonomous, Tyre, Bronze, 108/109 CE

Weight: 3.21 g
Diameter: 14 mm x 16 mm
Axis: 12
Obv design: Bust of Tyche, r., wearing turreted crown, veil, an earring; (perhaps behind, palm-branch); border of dots.
Rev legend: ΜΗ Τ[ΡΟΠΟΛΕΩΣ] ΙΕΡΑΣ
Rev design: Palm-tree with two bunches of fruit; across field, date (ΔΛ-Σ); around, from l. upwards, inscr.; border of dots.
Literature: *BMC Phoen*: 265, No 340–42

[10] 138736 | B22564 | L2249 | F57 | Area A West

Agrippa II, Paneas, Bronze, 82/83 CE

Weight: 1.86 g
Diameter: 13 mm
Axis: 12
Obv legend: BA AΓP on r.
Obv design: Bust of Tyche, r., veiled;
Rev design: One cornucopiae; across field: ET ΔΛ (year 82/83 CE)
Literature: *TJC*: 240, No 178

[11] 138737 | B22584 | L2251 | G57 | Area A West

Philip I or II, Antioch (Syria), Bronze, 244/249 CE

Weight: 15.14 g
Diameter: 18 mm
Axis: 6
Obv legend: AVTOK K MIOVΛIΦIΛIΠΠIOC CEB
Obv design: Head of Philip, l., wreathed;
Rev legend: ANTIOXEΩ — MHTPOKΟΛΩΛI
Rev design: across field: Δ-E | S-C
Comment: Rev: second letter N missing in our coin, but third letter N exists.
Literature: Cf. *BMC Syria*: 215, No 530; Cf. Butcher 2004: 397, No 498 (no examples missing second N) NB: The BMC ref is mistaken?

[12] 138738 | B22599 | 2253 | G57 | Area A West

Demetrius I, Tyre, Bronze, 153/152 BCE

Weight: 2.46 g
Diameter: 16 mm
Axis: 12
Obv design: Diademed head of Demetrius I, r., diadem ends falling straight behind, dotted border.
Rev legend: BΑΣ[I]A[E]ΩΣ — [ΔHM]HTPIOY
Rev design: BΑΣIAEΩΣ (curving) on r., ΔHMHTPIOY (curving) on l., palm tree, dotted border; Ξ-P in field.
Literature: *SC II*: 180, No 1676.4

[13] 138739 | B31013 | L4000 | B/C70 | Area T

Al-Nasir Yusuf Salah al-Din, Sultanate of Egypt, Ayyubid Dynasty, Bronze, AH 585 (=1189 CE)

Weight: 5.71 g
Diameter: 24 mm
Axis:
Obv design: (center:) almalik / alnasir (margin illegible)
Rev design: (centre:) yusuf / bin-ayub
Literature: Cf. Balog 1980: 93, No 145

[14] 138740 | B31016 | L4000 | B/C70 | Area T

Al-Nasir Yusuf Salah al-Din, Sultanate of Egypt, Ayyubid Dynasty, Bronze, AH 589 (=1193 CE)

Weight: 5.39 g
Diameter: 23 mm x 25 mm
Axis:
Obv design: (center:) almalik / alnasir (margin missing)
Rev design: (centre:) yusuf / bin-ayub (margin illegible)
Literature: Cf. Balog 1980: 93, No 148

[15] 138741 | B21886 | L5728 | A/B27 | Area C

Ptolemy III, Tyre, Bronze, hole-centered, 246–222 BCE

Weight: 3.93 g
Diameter: 17 mm x 19 mm
Axis: 12
Rev legend: BΑΣ[I]AEΩΣ] - ΠITOΛEMAIOY
Rev design: In left field: club
Literature: Lorber, forthcoming, No B466

[16] 138742 | B21877 | L 5731 | B/C27 | Area C

Demetrius II, Tyre, Bronze, 144/143 BCE

Weight: 2.11 g
Diameter: 12 mm x 14 mm
Axis: 12
Obv design: Diademed head of Demetrius II, r., diadem ends falling straight behind, dotted border.
Rev legend: BΑΣIAEΩΣ — ΔHMHTPIOY

Rev design: ΒΑΣΙΛΕΩΣ (curving) on r., ΔΗΜΗΤΡΙΟΥ (curving) on l., palm tree, dotted border. In field: Θ–ΞΡ.
Literature: SC II: 304, No 1970.3

[17] 138743 | B21882 | L5732 | A29 | Area C
Ptolemy I, Alexandria, Bronze, 305/304 BCE–283/282 BCE
Weight: 9.86 g
Diameter: 25 mm
Axis: 12
Rev legend: ΒΑΣΙΛΕΩ[Σ] — [ΠΤΟΛΕ]ΜΑΙΟΥ

[18] 138835 | B6753 | L1529 | H54 | Area A South
Antioch (Syria), bronze
Weight: 12.41 g
Diameter: 33 mm
Axis: 12
Obv legend: [ΑΥΤ]ΟΚ Κ ΜΙΟΥΦΙΛΛΙΠΟΣ ΣΕΒ
Rev legend: ΑΝΤΙΟΧΕΩΝ - ΜΗΤΡΟΚΟΛΩ
Rev design: Ram/deer jumping, r.; In fields: Δ–Ε and Σ–C.
Literature: Butcher, 2004: 397, No 498

[19] (no IAA #) | B11092 | L1123 (T280) | G58 | Area A West
Set of 5 Ottoman coins. [Field diary reads 3 silver Ottoman coins]

[20] (no IAA #) | B22551 | L2246 | F58 | Area A West
Unidentified coin

[21] (no IAA #) | B23543 | L2249 | F57 | Area A West
Modern, Silver

[22] (no IAA #) | B22597 | L2249 | F57 | Area A West
Modern, Silver

[23] (no IAA #) | B22491 | L2241 | G57 | Area A West
Unidentified coin

2011 Season (16 coins)

[01] 138125 | B23425 | L2205 | E56 | Area A West
Ptolemy III, Alexandria, Bronze, 220 BCE
Weight: 4.10 g
Diameter: 17 mm
Axis: 12
Obv design: Head of Zeus Ammon, r. with diadem and floral ornament; dotted border.
Rev legend: [ΒΑΣΙΛΕΩΣ — ΠΤΟΛΕ]ΜΑΙΟΥ[Υ]
Rev design: Eagle, l. on thunderbolt, at shoulder cornucopiae; between legs, monogram 1; dotted border.
Literature: *SNG Ptol*: Pl VII, 181

[02] 138126 | B23432 | L2205 | E56 | Area A West
Ptolemy (?), Bronze, 323–31 BCE
Weight: 15.14 g
Diameter: 27 mm
Axis: 12
Obv design: Head of Ptolemy (?), r.
Rev design: Eagle, l.

[03] 138127 | B23438 | L2205 | E56 | Area A West

Hasmonean, Jerusalem, Bronze, 135–37 BCE

Weight: 1.75 g
Diameter: 13 mm x 17 mm
Axis: 12
Obv legend: [...] || [...] || [...]
Obv design: Paleo-Hebrew inscr. within wreath
Rev design: Double cornucopiae with pomegranite between

[04] 138128 | B23444 | L2205 | E56 | Area A West

Alexander Jannaeus (YNTN), Jerusalem, Bronze, 104–76 BCE

Weight: 1.95 g
Diameter: 15 mm
Axis: 12
Obv design: Traces of paleo-Hebrew inscription in wreath, over-struck on a previous coin depicting lily with half of the original inscription
Rev design: Traces of double cornucopiae with a pomegranate between the horns, over-struck on previous coin depicting anchor surrounded by Greek inscription.
Literature: *TJC*: 217, Group T (actually p 216)

[05] 138129 | B23455 | L2205 | E56 | Area A West

Roman Provincial, (Decapolis?), Bronze, 200–299 CE

Weight: 11.60 g
Diameter: 25 mm
Axis: 12
Obv legend: [...]
Obv design: Bust, r.
Rev legend: [...]
Rev design: Bust, r.

[06] 138130 | B23284 | L2222 | G55 | Area A West

Severus Alexander, Ako-Ptolemais, Bronze, 222–235 CE

Weight: 6.68 g
Diameter: 21 mm
Axis: 6
Obv legend: [IMP CAE M AVR SEV ALEX]AN[DER AVG]
Obv design: Bust of Severus Alexander, r., laureate, draped and cuirassed
Rev legend: [COLO] PTOLE (Colonia Ptolemais)
Rev design: Emperor on horseback advancing l.; right hand raised; scepter in l. hand; cloak trails behind; caduceus below the horse's raised foreleg.
Literature: Jenks 2013. Kadman 1961: 130–31, No 191 (Cf. 192 for obv & rev legend: *obv*: Ditto, but emperor cuirassed with shield against shoulder; IMP CAE M AVR SEV ALEXANDER. *rev*: Ditto, but caduceus before foot of horse. Rev. type 51.

[07] 138131 | B23367 | L2229 | G57 | Area A West

Elagabalus, Tyre, Bronze, 218–222 CE (after suppression of colony)

Weight: 16.18 g
Diameter: 29 mm
Axis: 12
Obv legend: IMP CAES M AV AN — TONIN[VS AVG]
Obv design: Bust of Elagabalus, r., laureate, wearing paludamentum and cuirass; around, inscr. IMPCAESMAVAN TONINVS AVG
Rev legend: TVR - I - O - RVM
Rev design: Astarte, wearing turreted crown, short chiton, and himation, standing to front, l. foot on prow; she places her r. on trophy, crowned by Nike; at her feet, on l. palm-tree, on r. murex-shell; around, inscr.: TV RI O RVM
Literature: *BMC Phoen*: 275, No 396

[08] 138132 | B23388 | L2229 | F57 | Area A West

Mamluk, Bronze

[09] 138133 | B23400 | L2229 | F57 | Area A West

Smoothed Roman Provincial coin with circular countermark, possibly 100–199 CE

Weight: 24.0 g
Diameter: 7.07 mm
Obv legend: [...]
Obv design: Bust, r.

[10] 138134 | B23416 | L2229 | F57 | Area A West

Severus Alexander (?), Tyre, Bronze, 222–235 CE

Weight: 7.99 g
Diameter: 27 mm
Axis: 11
Obv design: Bust of Severus Alexander, r., bareheaded, wearing paludamentum and cuirass; inscr.: M•AV•ALEXAN D[ER]•CAES•SE
Rev legend: SEPTV[RO - - -]
Rev design: Astarte, wearing turreted crown, short chiton, and himation, standing to front, l. foot on prow; she places her r. on trophy, crowned by Nike; at her feet, on l. 'Marsyas' r., on r. murex-shell; inscr.: SEP TVR -- COL
Literature: Cf. *BMC Phoen*: 279, No 419

[11] 138135 | B23440 | L2229 | F57 | Area A West

Smoothed Roman Provincial coin with elliptical countermark, possibly 200–299 CE

Weight: 13.99 g
Diameter: 24 mm x 27 mm
Obv design: Bust, r.
Rev design: Blank

[12] (no IAA #) | B23347 | L2208

Modern Syrian, 10 Piastres, 1948 CE

[13] (no IAA #) | B23378 | L2230 | F56 | Area A West

Coin-shaped ornament

[14] (no IAA #) | B23415 | L2229 | F58 | Area A West

Abd ūl-Hāmīd, silver, pierced

[15] (no IAA #) | B23450 | L2205 | E56 | Area A West

Abd ūl-Hāmīd, silver, 1774–1789 CE

[16] (no IAA #) | B23439 | 2229 | F57 | Area A West

Unidentified coin. Small bevelled bronze, Tyre (199–100 BCE) or Jerusalem (Hasmonean, 135–37 BCE)

2010 Season (14 coins)

[01] 137117 | B11029 | L1102 | G58 | Area A South

Ottoman (not fully identified), Para, Silver, 1600–1699 CE

Weight: 0.54 g
Diameter: 14 mm x 16 mm
Obv design: Tughra
Rev design: Illegible

[02] 137118 | B23022 | L2201 | F55 | Area A West

Antoninus Pius, Rome, aureus, Gold, 138 CE (between 25 February and 10 July)

Weight: 7.17 g
Diameter: 20 mm
Axis: 6
Obv legend: IMP T AEL CAES ANTONINVS
Obv design: Antoninus Pius, r.; draped bust, bare and bearded
Rev legend: TRI POT COS DES II
Rev design: Pietas, steps in front of an altar decorated with round small objects (flowers?); r. hand raised above the altar; holds a container of perfumes in her l. hand
Literature: Arav & Savage 2011: 135

[03] 137119 | B23077 | L2206 | F56 | Area A West

Herod, Jerusalem, Bronze, prutah, 37–4 BCE

Weight: 1.60 g
Diameter: 15 mm
Axis: 6
Obv legend: around: [HPΩΔΟΥ ΒΑCΙΑE]
Obv design: Anchor
Rev design: Double cornucopiae with caduceus between horns; above, five pellets. No dots visible, but N visible.
Literature: *TJC*: 222–23, No 59

[04] 137120 | B23271 | L2210 | F56 | Area A West

Seleucid? (mint uncertain), Bronze, 199–63 BCE

Weight: 5.36 g
Diameter: 20 mm
Axis: 12
Obv design: Head, r.
Rev design: Galley to l. (perhaps a figure standing on the galley and perhaps letters above)
Literature: Lorber (6, 2012) concurs

[05] 137121 | B23188 | L2213 | F55 | Area A West

Hasmonean, Jerusalem, Bronze, 135–37 BCE

Weight: 2.00 g
Diameter: 13 mm
Axis: 12
Obv legend: [...] | [...] | [...]
Obv design: Paleo-Hebrew inscr. within wreath
Rev design: Double cornucopiae with pomegranite between

[06] 137122 | B23272 | L2215 | G58 | Area A West

Hasmonean, Jerusalem, Bronze, 135–37 BCE

Weight: 1.22 g
Diameter: 14 mm x 16 mm
Axis: 6
Obv legend: [...] | [...] | [...]
Obv design: Paleo-Hebrew inscr. within wreath
Rev design: Double cornucopiae with pomegranite between

[07] 137124 | B21811 | L5718 | E25 | Area C

Demetrius II, Tyre, Bronze, 146/145 BCE

Weight: 1.96 g
Diameter: 13 mm
Obv design: Brockage. Negative version of opp die visible.
Rev legend: ΒΑΣΙΛΕΩΣ (curving) on r., [ΔΗΜΗΤΡΙΟΥ] (curving) on l.
Rev design: Palm tree, dotted border. In field: [L]ZE-P
Literature: *SC* 2: 304, No 1970.1

[08] (no IAA #) | B11011 | L1101 | I58 | Area A South
Ottoman coin

[09] (no IAA #) | B11026 | L1105 | G58 | Area A South
Ottoman coin

[10] (no IAA #) | B23124 | L2200 | G55 | Area A West
Unidentified coin, Bronze

[11] (no IAA #) | B23251 | L2217 | F55 | Area A West
Modern coin, Unidentified, Bronze

[12] (no IAA #) | (no basket) | Surface Find
Mahmud II (Ottoman), Qustantiniyeh, Silver on Paralik noktasiz, 1833 CE

[13] (no IAA #) | (no basket) | Surface Find
Unidentified coin, Bronze

[14] (no IAA #) | (no basket) | Surface Find
Unidentified coin, Bronze

2009 Season (10 coins)

[01] 104759 | B21619 | L2082 | C54 | Area A
Herod Philip, Paneas, Bronze, 8/9 CE (or 15/16 CE)
Weight: 4.60 g
Diameter: 19 mm
Axis: 6
Obv legend: KAICAPI CEBAΣTΩ
Obv design: Head of Augustus, r., laureate;
Rev legend: inscription starting on l. turning outwards: ΦΙΛΙΠΠΙΟΥ ΤΕΤΡΑΡΧΟΥ
Rev design: Facade of tetrastyle temple standing on platform (the Augusteum in Paneas), the columns with ionic capitals; in pediment, pellet; between columns, date: LIB (year 12 = 8/9 CE)
Literature: Cf. *TJC*: 228, No 97

[02] 104760 | B21021 | L2095 | P49 | Area A
Roman Provincial, Aka-Ptolemais, Bronze, 1–199 CE
Weight: 9.10 g
Diameter: 25 mm
Obv design: Head, r.

[03] 104761 | B21658 | L2150 | D54 | Area A
Claudius, Tiberias, Bronze, 53/54 CE
Weight: 12.92 g
Diameter: 23 mm
Axis: 12
Obv legend: [ΚΛΑΥΔΙΟΥ — Κ]ΑΙCΑΡΟC
Obv design: Palm branch; across field, date: ΛΙΓ (year 13 = 53 CE)
Rev legend: [ΤΙΒΕ] | [ΠΙ]ΑC
Rev design: Inscription in wreath
Literature: *TJC*: 261, No 347

[04] 104762 | B21658 | L2150 | D54 | Area A
Antipas, Tiberias, Bronze, 28/29 CE
Weight: 10.58 g
Diameter: 23 x 25 mm
Obv legend: starting below, l.: ΗΡΩΔ[ΟΥ — ΤΕΤΡΑ]ΡΧΟΥ

Obv design: Palm branch; in the field, date: [L] ΛΓ (year 33 = 28/9 CE)
Rev legend: TIBE | P[I]A[C]
Rev design: Inscription in wreath
Literature: *TJC*: 226, No 79

[05] 104763 | B21658 | L2150 | D54 | Area A

Claudius, Tiberias, Bronze, 53/54 CE

Weight: 11.62 g
Diameter: 21 x 23 mm
Obv legend: [ΚΛΑΥΔΙΟΥ — ΚΑΙΣΑΡΟΣ]
Obv design: Palm branch; across field, date: ΛΙΓ (year 13 = 53 CE)
Rev legend: [TIBE] | [PIAC]
Rev design: Inscription in wreath
Literature: *TJC*: 261, No 347

[06] 104764 | B21669 | L2150 | D54 | Area A

Otacilia Severa, Damascus, Bronze, 244–249 CE

Weight: 22.49 g
Diameter: 30 mm
Axis: 12
Obv legend: [MOTAC] SEVERA A[VG]
Obv design: Bust of Otacilia Severa, r.
Rev legend: [COL] DAM — AC METRO
Rev design: Wolf, r., suckling Romulus and Remus; behind, vexillum inscribed: (line 1) LEGV, (line 2) IFRE
Literature: *BMC Syria*: 286, No 25

[07] 104765 | B21657 | L2153 | E54 | Area A

Roman Provincial, Bronze, 1–299 CE

Weight: 5.02 g
Diameter: 21 x 23 mm

[08] 104766 | B21686 | L2158 | D54 | Area A

Antoninus Pius, Rome, Silver, 153/154 CE

Weight: 3.43 g
Diameter: 19 mm
Axis: 6
Obv legend: [AVRELIVS CAE]SAR AVG PII [F]
Obv design: Head of Marcus Aurelius, bare, r.
Rev legend: [TR POT / VIII / COS II]
Rev design: Unclear. Appears to be Spes.
Literature: Cf. *CRE* IV: 120, No 822

[09] 104767 | B22738 | L2178 | F54 | Area A

Antiochus III, Ptolemais, Bronze, 198–187 BCE

Weight: 1.82 g
Diameter: 11 mm
Axis: 12
Obv design: Laureate head of Apollo, r., dotted border.
Rev legend: [B]ΑΣΙΑΕ[ΩΣ /ANTIOXΟΥ]
Rev design: Incomplete or blundered legend, Apollo standing l., testing arrow and resting hand on grounded bow.
Literature: *SC* 1: 416, No 1096

[10] 137123 | B21725 | L5716 | E25 | Area C

Seleucid, Tyre, Bronze, 154/153–144/43 BCE

Weight: 2.21 g
Diameter: 17 mm
Axis: 12
Obv design: Diademed head of Demetrius I, r., diadem ends falling straight behind, dotted border.

Rev legend: [ΒΑΣΙ]Α[ΕΩΣ] (curving) on r., [ΔΗΜΗΤΡΙΟΥ] (curving) on l.
Rev design: Palm tree, dotted border. In field: [?]Ε-Ρ.
Literature: Cf. *SC* 2: 180, No 1676.4

2008 Season (26 coins)

[01] 125043 | B18519 | L0001

Ptolemy III, Tyre, Bronze, 246–222 BCE

Weight: 5.36 g
Diameter: 20 mm
Axis: 12
Obv design: Head of Zeus Ammon, r. with diadem and floral ornament; dotted border.
Rev legend: ΒΑΣ[ΙΛΕΩΣ — ΠΤΟΛΕΜΑΙΟΥ]
Rev design: Eagle l. on thunderbolt; in front (? l.), club; dotted border.
Literature: *SNG Ptolemies*: Pl. XVII, 496; Lorber *PC* 1: B465

[02] 125044 | B16886 | L1583 | F26 | Area C

Antiochus III, Uncertain mint 61 in southern Coele-Syria, Bronze, 222–187 BCE

Weight: 4.22 g
Diameter: 15 mm
Axis: 12
Obv design: Laureate head of Apollo, r., with short straight hair, dotted border.
Rev legend: [ΒΑΣΙΛΕΩΣ] on r., [ΑΝΤΙΟΧΟΥ] on l.
Rev design: Horse trotting, dotted border.
Literature: *SC* 1: 415, No 1094

[03] 125045 | B16856 | L1584 | F26 | Area C

Seleucid, Tyre, Bronze, 399–200 BCE

Weight: 1.63 g
Diameter: 8 mm
Axis: 12
Obv design: Laureate head, r. of Antiochus III as Apollo
Rev legend: [Β]Α[Σ]ΙΛΕ[ΩΣ - ΑΝΤΙΟΧΟΥ]
Rev design: Apollo standing l., testing arrow and resting l. hand on grounded bow
Literature: Cf. *SC* 1: 401, No 1081 (seems to be 1051)

[04] 125046 | B18253 | L2056 | C53 | Area A

Antiochus V, Tyre, Bronze, 172–161 BCE

Weight: 1.87 g
Diameter: 9 mm
Axis: 11
Obv design: Diademed head of Demetrius I, r., diadem ends falling straight behind, dotted border.
Rev legend: [ΒΑ]ΣΙΛΕ[ΩΣ] curving on r., [ΑΝΤΙΟΧΟΥ] (curving) on l.
Rev design: Palm tree, dotted border. date (across field): \overline{N} -P or \overline{LN} -P (S.E. 150 = 163/2 BCE).
Literature: Cf. *SC* 2: 136, No 1580

[05] 125047 | B18513 | L2052 | C53 | Area A

Gordian III, Gadara, Bronze, 238–244 CE

Weight: 11.75 g
Diameter: 25 mm
Axis: 10
Obv legend: ΑΥΤΟΚ · Κ · Μ Α [C ANTW ΓΟΡΔΙΑΝΟC]
Obv design: Bust, r., laureate, wearing paludamentum and curiaiss, shown from the rear.
Rev legend: Above, in three lines: ΠΟΜΠΙ ΓΑΔΑΡΕ WN; below, ΓΤ
Rev design: Galley, with captain, row of oarsmen and steersman on deck, sailing r.
Literature: Spijkerman 1978: 152–53, No 93

[06] 125048 | B18622 | L2061 | C53 | Area A

Mahmud b. Zangi, Damascus, Bronze, AH 541–569 (1146–11774 CE)

Weight: 5.39 g
Diameter: 20 mm x 24 mm
Obv design: (Arabic)
Rev design: (Arabic)
Literature: Cf. *BMCO* III: 212, No 602 (page and item # were reversed on the card)

[07] 125049 | B18623 | L2061 | C53 | Area A

Frederick Henry, Prince of Orange, Silver, 1627–1647 CE

Weight: 8.26 g
Diameter: 30 mm
Axis: 3
Obv legend: FRED HENR • D • G • PRINAVR • COM • NASS
Obv design: Bust nu et barbu a droite.
Rev legend: SOLI • DEO • HONOR • ET • GLOR
Rev design: Ecusson couronné
Literature: Cf. Poey D'Avant, II: 408, No 4605; H. J. Van der Wiel 1973: 74, No 63 probably p 112

[08] 125050 | B18564 | L2061 | C53 | Area A

Autonomous, Gaba, (or Paneas, but not Sidon), Bronze, 100–199 CE

Weight: 4.25 g
Diameter: 15 mm
Axis: 6
Obv design: Veiled head of Tyche, l.
Rev design: Tetrastyle temple.
Literature: Cf. *BMC Phoen*: cviii, Pl. XLII, No 16 (coin in Berlin); *RPC* 1: 654, No 4602.

[09] 125051 | B18585 | L2065 | H55 | Area A

Roman Provincial, Bronze, 1–99 CE

Weight: 8.29 g
Diameter: 20 mm x 24 mm
Obv design: Head, r.

[10] 125052 | B18616 | L2067 | H54/55 | Area A

Commodus, Tiberias, Bronze, 188/189 CE (? 189/190 CE)

Weight: 14.06 g
Diameter: 25 mm
Axis: 10
Obv legend: Around from l. below: [AYT K M AVP KOMOΔOV]
Obv design: Bust of Commodus, r., bearded and laureate, wearing paludamentum and cuirass; border of dots.
Rev legend: Around from l. below: [TIB KA CYP ΠΙΑΑ]
Rev design: City-goddess (Tyche-Fortuna) wearing turreted crown, long chiton and peplos, standing to l., r. hand resting on rudder, holding cornucopiae in l. hand; border of dots; across field, date: ET PO = year 170 (of the era of Tiberias = 188/89 CE).
Literature: Kindler 1961: 61, No 14; Meshorer, Bijovsky & Fischer-Bossert 2013: 71, No 15

[11] 125053 | B18649 | L2069 | H54/55 | Area A

Antiochus III, Tyre, Bronze, 199/198–189/188 BCE

Weight: 6.82 g
Diameter: 20 mm
Axis: 12
Obv design: Diademed head of Antiochus III, r., with mature to elderly features and baldness at temple, dotted border.
Rev legend: [ΒΑΣΙΛΕΩΣ] above [ANTIOXΟΥ] below
Rev design: Stern of galley, r., dotted border.
Literature: *SC* 1: 410, No 1078

[12] 125054 | B18659 | L2069 | H54/55 | Area A

Seleucid, unknown mint, Bronze, 399–200 BCE

Weight: 4.6 g
Diameter: 20 mm
Obv design: Head, r.
Rev design: Illegible

[13] 125055 | B18667 | L2069 | H54/55 | Area A

Alexander Jannaeus, Jerusalem, Bronze, 104–76 BCE

Weight: 0.79 g
Diameter: 8 mm
Obv legend: [ΑΛΕΞΑΝΔΡΟΥ ΒΑΣΙΛΕΩΣ] (of King Alexander)
Obv design: Anchor, surrounded by inscription.
Rev legend: Between rays of star, paleo Hebrew inscription: יהנתנהמלך (Yehonatan the King)
Rev design: Eight-pointed star in diadem.
Literature: *TJC*: 209–10, Group K

[14] 125056 | B18670 | L2069 | H54/55 | Area A

Hasmonean, Jerusalem, Bronze, 135–37 BCE

Weight: 1.20 g
Diameter: 8 mm
Axis: 6
Obv legend: [...] | [...] | ולית | [...]
Obv design: Paleo-Hebrew inscr. within wreath
Rev design: Double cornucopiae with pomegranite between

[15] 125057 | B18707 | L2069 | H54/55 | Area A

Hasmonean, Jerusalem, Bronze, 135–37 BCE

Weight: 1.46 g
Diameter: 9 mm
Obv legend: [...] | [...] | [...]
Obv design: Paleo-Hebrew inscr. within wreath
Rev legend: Illegible

[16] 125058 | 18709 | L2069 | H54/55 | Area A

Herod, Jerusalem, Bronze, 37–4 BCE

Weight: 1.22 g
Diameter: 8 mm
Axis: 12
Obv legend: around: [HPΩΔΟΥ ΒΑΣΙΛΕ]]
Obv design: Anchor
Rev design: Double cornucopiae with caduceus between horns; above, five pellets.
Literature: *TJC*: 222–23, No 59

[17] 125059 | B18710 | L2069 | H54/55 | Area A

Alexander Jannaeus, Jerusalem, Bronze, 104–76 BCE

Weight: 1.74 g
Diameter: 8 mm x 10 mm
Obv legend: [ΑΛΕΞΑΝΔΡΟΥ ΒΑΣΙΛΕΩΣ] (of King Alexander)
Obv design: Anchor, surrounded by inscription.
Rev legend: Between rays of star, paleo Hebrew inscription: יהנתנהמלך (Yehonatan the King)
Rev design: Eight-pointed star in diadem.
Literature: *TJC*: 209–10, Group K

[18] 125060 | 18711 | L2069 | H54/55 | Area A

Herod, Jerusalem, Bronze, 37–4 BCE

Weight: 1.10 g
Diameter: 7 mm x 9 mm
Axis: 6
Obv legend: around: [HPΩΔΟΥ ΒΑΣΙΛΕ]]

Obv design: Anchor.
Rev design: Double cornucopiae with caduceus between horns; above, five pellets.
Literature: *TJC*: 222–23, No 59

[19] 125061 | B18731 | L2069 | H54/55 | Area A

Ptolemy II, Tyre, Bronze, hole centered, 283–246 BCE

Weight: 68.8 g
Diameter: 50 mm
Axis: 12
Obv design: Head of Zeus Ammon, r. with diadem and floral ornament; dotted border.
Rev legend: BA[ΣΙΑΕΩΣ] — ΠΤΟΛΕΜΑ[ΙΟΥ]
Rev design: Eagle, l. on thunderbolt; in front, club; dotted border.
Literature: Lorber PC 1: B461; *SNG Ptolemies* Pl XVII, 493 (2009 updated to Ptolemy III – as per Lorber, forthcoming)

[20] 125062 | B18697 | L2070 | G54 | Area A

Domitian, Caesarea Maritima, Bronze, 81–96 CE

Weight: 14.14 g
Diameter: 25 mm
Axis: 12
Obv legend: [IMP DOMI]TIANVS CAES AVG GERMAN[ICVS]
Obv design: Head of Domitian, r., laureate.
Rev design: Minerva standing on galley r., holding shield in l. and spear in r.; on l., trophy; on r., palm branch; between Minerva and prow of galley, small owl.
Literature: *TJC*: 267, No 391

[21] 125063 | B18728 | L2070 | G54 | Area A

Roman Provincial, Bronze, 1–299 CE

Weight: 4.38 g
Diameter: 20 mm

[22] 125064 | B18683 | L2073 | C/D 53/54 | Area A

Autonomous, Tyre, Bronze, 121/122 CE

Weight: 3.76 g
Diameter: 15 mm x 17 mm
Axis: 12
Obv design: Bust of Tyche, r., wearing turreted crown, veil and earrings; behind, palm-branch; border of dots,
Rev legend: around, from l. upwards: IEPA — MH[T]ΠΟΠΟΑΙC
Rev design: Palm-tree with two branches of fruit; across field, date; border of dots. In field: ZM–C.
Literature: *BMC Phoen*: 266, No 346

[23] 125065 | B18682 | L2076 | C/D 53/54 | Area A

Seleucid, Tyre, Bronze, 222–126 BCE

Weight: 1.98 g
Diameter: 10 mm
Axis: 12
Obv design: Diademed head of Antiochus III, r., with mature to elderly features and baldness at temple, dotted border.
Rev legend: [ΒΑΣΙΛΕ]ΩΣ - [ANTIOXΟΥ] around
Rev design: Palm tree, dotted border.
Literature: Cf. *SC* 1: 411, No 1081

[24] 125066 | B18715 | L2070 | G54 | Area A

Roman Provincial, Bronze, 1–199 CE

Weight: 12.18 g
Diameter: 22 mm x 25 mm

[25] no IAA # | Basket | L2068 | A/B52 | Area A

Maria Theresia, Austria, Bronze, 1740–1780 CE

Weight:

Diameter:

[26] no IAA # | B18205 | L2024 | E54 | Area A

Unidentified modern coin, Bronze

Weight:

Diameter:

2007 Season (11 coins)

[01] 115955 | B16167 | L1578 | B26/27 | Area C

Antiochus III, Tyre, Bronze, hole-centered, 222–187 BCE

Weight: 8.22 g

Diameter: 22 mm

Axis: 12

Obv design: Diademed head of Antiochus III, r., with mature to elderly features and baldness at temple, dotted border.

Rev legend: [ΒΑΣΙΛΕΩΣ] above, ANTIOXOY below

Rev design: Stern of galley, r., dotted border.

Literature: SC 1: 410, No 1078

[02] 115956 | B17804 | L1760 | P51/52 | Area A

Seleucid, Bronze, 299–100 BCE

Weight: 2.46 g

Diameter: 16 mm x 18 mm

Rev design: In left field: L

[03] 115959 | B18339 | L2025 | C/D 53/54 | Area A

Alexander I Balas, Tyre, Bronze, hole-centered, 147/146 BCE

Weight: 1.65 g

Diameter: 13 mm

Axis: 12

Obv design: Diademed head of Alexander I, r., diadem ends falling straight behind, dotted border.

Rev legend: [ΒΑΣΙΛΕΩΣ] curving on r., [ΑΛΕΞ]ΑΝ[ΔΡΟΥ] curving on l.,

Rev design: Palm tree, dotted border. Date (across field): ΣΕ-[Ρ] (S.E. 164 = 149/8 BCE).

Literature: SC 2: 242, No 1838.2

[04] 115960 | B18445 | L2035 | I54 | Area A

Roman Provincial, Bronze, 1–199 CE

Weight: 8.37 g

Diameter: 23 mm x 25 mm

Axis: 12

Obv design: Head, r.

Rev design: Figure, r.

[05] 115961 | B18453 | L2035 | I54 | Area A

Seleucid, Tyre, Bronze, 166/165 BCE

Weight: 5.76 g

Diameter: 18 mm x 20 mm

Axis: 12

Obv design: Diademed head of Antiochus IV, r., star above diadem, one diadem end flying up behind (beneath date), the other falling forward over shoulder, stars at ends of diadem, dotted border. Date (behind head): ΔMP (S.E. 144 = 169/8 BCE)

Rev legend: [ΒΑΣΙΛΕΩΣ ANTIOXOY ΤΥΡΙΩΝ]

Rev design: Above in three lines. Phoenician inscr. (of Tyre, mother [ie., metropolis] of the Sidonians); below, stern of galley, l., with railing, oar, and aplaston, dotted border.

Literature: Cf. SC 1: 410, No 1079 (as below, 115963); Cf. SC 2: 86, No 1463 (as here)

[06] 115962 | B18367 | L2039 | D53/54 | Area A

Alexander the Great, Bronze, 330–300 BCE

Weight: 2.79 g

Diameter: 14 mm x 16 mm

Axis: 12

Obv design: Head of Hercules, r.

Rev design: Above: Club to r., below: quiver.

Literature: Price 1991

[07] 115963 | B18372 | L2039 | D53/54 | Area A

Seleucid, Tyre, Bronze, 200–150 BCE

Weight: 4.47 g

Diameter: 20 mm

Axis: 12

Obv design: Diademed head of Antiochus III, r., with mature to elderly features and baldness at temple, dotted border.

Rev legend: [BAΣΙΑΛΕΩΣ] above [ANTIOXOY] below

Rev design: Prow l. with pointed S-curved acrostolium, terminated on r. by dolphin swimming downward, second small dolphin depicted beneath ship's "eye," dotted border.

Literature: Cf. *SC* 1: 410, No 1079

[08] 115964 | B18406 | L2046 | C54 | Area A

Early Byzantine, Folis, Bronze, pierced, 500–599 CE

Weight: 7.1 g

Diameter: 26 mm x 28 mm

Axis: 6

Obv design: Bust, r.

Rev design: M (40)

[09] 115965 | B18408 | L2048 | C/D54 | Area A

Roman Provincial, Bronze, 1–199 CE [delete Hole-centered]?

Weight: 6.56 g

Diameter: 20 mm x 22 mm

Axis: 12

Obv design: Bust, r.

Rev design: Standing figure

[10] 115975 | B16813 | L1580 | E25 | Area C

Seleucid, Tyre (?), Bronze, hole-centered, worn, 222–126 BCE

Weight: 2.08 g

Diameter: 14 mm

Axis: 12

Obv design: Head, r.

Rev design: Palm tree (?)

[11] 115978 | B18371 | L2043 | C/D54 | Area A

Ottoman, Damascus, Bronze, 1300–1918 CE

Weight: 0.98 g

Diameter: 14 mm

Obv legend: (blank)

Obv design: (effaced)

Rev legend: (blank)

Rev design: (Arabic)

2006 Season (8 coins)

[01] 115958 | B18070 | L2007 | N48 | Area A

Ptolemaic, Bronze

Weight: 13.14 g
Diameter: 26 mm
Axis: 12
Obv design: Head, r.
Rev legend: B[ΑΣΙΑΕΩΣ — ΠΤΟΛΕΜΑΙΟΥ]

[02] 115966 | B18065 | L2007 | W of Area | Area A West

Roman Provincial, Bronze, 1–299 CE

Weight: 5.13 g
Diameter: 18 mm x 22 mm
Obv legend: [...]
Obv design: Head or bust, r.
Rev legend: (blank)

[03] 115970 | B16132 | L569 | C/D25 | Area C

Antiochus III, Sardes, Bronze, 222–187 BCE

Weight: 2.71 g
Diameter: 12 mm x 14 mm
Axis: 10
Obv design: Laureate head of Apollo, r., hair knotted in krobylos behind, long wavy locks falling loose on neck, dotted border.
Rev legend: [B]ΑΣΙΑΕ[ΩΣ] above, ANTIO[XOY] below
Rev design: Elephant, l.
Literature: *SC* 1: 374, No 978

[04] 115971 | B16146 | L569 | C/D25 | Area C

Autonomous, Tyre, Silver, 450–400 BCE

Weight: 0.3 g
Diameter: 8 mm
Axis: 12
Obv design: Dolphin, r., cable border.
Rev design: Owl standing r., head facing over its l. shoulder, with crook and flail; cable border; slight incuse circle.
Literature: Cf. *BMC Phoen*: 227, No 4

[05] 115972 | (no basket) | L569 | C/D25 | Area C

Hasmonean, Jerusalem, Bronze, 135–37 BCE

Weight: 2.6 g
Diameter: 14 mm
Axis: 6
Obv legend: Wreath
Obv design: (Paleo-Hebrew text in 4 lines)
Rev design: Double cornucopiae with pomegranite between

[06] 115973 | B16127 | L572 | Area C

Hasmonean, Jerusalem, Bronze, 135–37 BCE

Weight: 2.56 g
Diameter: 14 mm
Axis: 2
Obv legend: Wreath
Obv design: (Paleo-Hebrew text in 4 lines)
Rev design: Double cornucopiae with pomegranite between

[07] 115974 | B16122 | L592 | Area C

Antiochus IV, Ptolemais, Bronze, serrated edge, 175–172 BCE

Weight: 4.27 g
Diameter: 18 mm
Axis: 12
Obv design: Veiled, diademed bust of Laodice IV, r., dotted border.
Rev legend: ΒΑΣΙΛΕΩΣ above, ANTIOXOY below
Rev design: Elephant head, l., dotted border.
Literature: SC 2: 90, No 1477

[08] 125042 | B16172 | L574 | D24 | Area C

Antiochus VII, Tyre, Silver, 139/138–138/137 BCE

Weight: 13.91 g
Diameter: 25 mm x 30 mm
Axis: 12
Obv design: Diademed and draped bust of Antiochus VII, r., diadem ends falling straight behind, dotted border.
Rev legend: ΒΑΣΙΛΕΩΣ (curving) on r., ANTIOXOY (curving) on l., around.
Rev design: Eagle standing l. on ship's ram, palm branch under far wing, dotted border. Date (r. field, below): EOP (S.E. 176 = 137/6 BCE).
Literature: SC 2: 384, No 2109 3

2005 Season (13 coins)

[01] 115957 | B18028 | L2003 | G53/54 | Area A

Roman Provincial, Bronze, 1–299 CE

Weight: 8.31 g
Diameter: 20 mm
Axis: 12
Obv design: Bust, r.
Rev design: Standing figure

[02] 115969 | B17524 | L1706 | O48 | Area A

Late Roman, Bronze, 317–498 CE

Weight: 1.97 g
Diameter: 18 mm
Axis: 6
Obv legend: [...] - NVS MAX AVG
Rev legend: [GLOR - IA EXERC] - ITVS
Rev design: 2 standards.
Literature: Cf. LRBC 1:28, No 1221

[03] 115976 | B18048 | L2004 | G53 | Area A

Ptolemaic, Bronze, hole-centered, 299–200 BCE

Weight: 9.22 g
Diameter: 23 mm
Axis: 12
Obv design: Head of Zeus Ammon, r.
Rev legend: [...]
Rev design: Eagle standing l. on thunderbolt. (unclear design to left)

[04] 115977 | B18062 | L2006 | H/G54 | Area A

Hasmonean, Jerusalem, Bronze, 135–37 BCE

Weight: 1.88 g
Diameter: 14 mm
Obv legend: Wreath with inscr.
Obv design: (Paleo-Hebrew text in 4 lines)
Rev design: Double cornucipiae with pomegranite between

[05] 136843 | B16071 | L563 | B26 | Area C

Seleucid, Tyre, Bronze, 222–126 BCE

Weight: 1.26 g
Diameter: 13 mm x 11 mm
Axis: 12
Obv design: Head, r.
Rev legend: [BAΣ]IΛEΩ[Σ] — [...]

[06] 136844 | B16067 | L564 | B/C/D26 | Area C

Seleucid, Tyre, Bronze, 222–126 BCE

Weight: 1.12 g
Diameter: 12 mm
Axis: 12
Obv design: Head, r.
Rev design: Palm tree. Field unclear or empty.

[07] 136845 | B17603 | L1708 | O56/57 | Area A

Seleucid, Tyre, Bronze, 222–126 BCE

Weight: 1.74 g
Diameter: 14 mm
Axis: 12
Obv design: Head, r.
Rev legend: [...]
Rev design: Palm tree?

[08] 136846 | B17525 | L1708 | O56/57 | Area A

Hadrian, Caesarea, Bronze, 117–138 CE

Weight: 8.00 g
Diameter: 21 mm
Axis: 6
Obv legend: [IMP TRA HADRIANO CAES AVG]
Obv design: Bust of Hadrian, laureate, draped.
Rev legend: [COL I FL AVG CAESARENS]
Rev design: Bust of Sarapis, r.,
Literature: Kadman 1957: 102–03, No 28

[09] 136847 | B17664 | L1724 | O/P47 | Area A

Herod Agrippa I, Jerusalem, Bronze, 41/42 CE

Weight: 1.70 g
Diameter: 17 mm
Obv legend: [ΑΓΡΗΠΠΑ ΒΑΣΙΛΕΩC]
Obv design: Canopy
Rev design: Three ears of grain issues from between two leaves; on l. and r., date: L ζ (year 6 = 41/2 CE)
Literature: *TJC*: 231, No 120

[10] 136848 | B18011 | L2001 | H54 | Area A

Hasmonean, Jerusalem, Bronze, 135–37 BCE

Weight: 2.55 g
Diameter: 16 mm
Axis: 10
Obv legend: Wreath with inscr.
Obv design: (Paleo-Hebrew text in 4 lines)
Rev design: Double cornucopiae with pomegranite between

[11] 136849 | B16076 | L563 | B26 | Area C

Autonomous, Ako-Ptolemais, Bronze, 112/111–111/110 BCE

Weight: 2.32 g
Diameter: 27 mm
Axis: 12
Obv design: Head of Apollo, r.
Rev legend: In 3 vertical lines: on l.: [ANTIOXEΩN] on r.: [TΩN] ENIT[ΘAEMAIΔI], in
exergue: [AΣ/KA]
Rev design: Lyre with three strings.
Literature: Cf. Kadman 1961: 100–01, No 50

[12] 136850 | B18004 | L2002 | G53 | Area A

Caracalla, Nysa-Scythopolis, Bronze, 206/207 CE

Weight: 15.38 g
Diameter: 27 mm
Axis: 12
Obv legend: From bottom l.: [AVT.K.MA — ANTWC EB]
Obv design: Bust of young Caracalla, r. laureate and draped.
Rev legend: NVCA - CKVO - IE . AC
Rev design: Tyche standing to r., turreted and wearing a chiton, with her l. foot on river-god
swimming r. within the central intercolumniation of a Corinthian tetrastyle temple with
pediment and arch; holding scepter in her r. hand and cornucopia in her l.; to l. and r. of
the pediment, O–C.
Literature: Barkay 2003: 213, No 49

[13] no IAA # | B17681 | L1724 | O/P47 | Area A

Modern coin, Bronze

2004 Season (3 coins)

[01] 115967 | B17502 | L1550 | L52 | Area A

Ptolemy II, Alexandria, Bronze, 272/271–266/265 BCE

Weight: 17.91 g
Diameter: 28 mm
Axis: 12
Obv design: Laureate head of Zeus, r.; border of dots. (Behind head as in SNG Ptol.)
Rev legend: ΒΑΣΙΛΕΩΣ ΠΤΟΛΕΜΑΙΟΥ
Rev design: Eagle, l. on thunder-bolt, wings open; in front, shield; border of dots. Above shield,
monogram 4; between legs, monogram 6.
Literature: *SNG Ptol*, PI IV: 119; Davesne 1989: 277

[02] 115968 | B20036 | L1702 | H54 | Area A

Ptolemy II, Alexandria, Bronze, 274/273–262/261 BCE

Weight: 10.83 g
Diameter: 26 mm
Axis: 12
Obv design: Laureate head of Zeus, r.; border of dots.
Rev legend: [ΒΑΣΙΛΕΩΣ — ΠΤΟΛΕ]ΜΑ[ΙΟΥ]
Rev design: Eagle, l. on thunder-bolt, wings open; in front, shield; border of dots. Above shield,
monogram 4; between legs, monogram 6.
Literature: Cf. *SNG Ptol*, PI IV: 119; Davesne 1989: 277

[03] 115979 | B17011 | On surface near temple | Area A

Autonomous, Bronze, 100 BCE–100 CE

Weight: 4.05 g
Diameter: 20 mm
Obv design: Head of Tyche, r.
Rev design: Illegible

2003 Season (10 coins)

[01] 136833 | B16455 | L1527 | O53 | Area A

Autonomous, Tyre, Bronze, 98/97 BCE–84/85 CE

Weight: 5.42 g
Diameter: 19 mm
Axis: 12
Obv design: Head of Tyche, r., wearing turreted crown, veil, and earring; behind, palm-branch; border of dots.
Rev legend: $\text{IEPA}\Sigma$ [ΑΣΥΛΟΥ]
Rev design: Galley, l., with prow terminating in volute, and aphlaston at stern; above, date, monogram [??]; below, Phoen. inscr. (lamed tsade resh); border of dots.
Literature: Cf. *BMC Phoen*: 255, No 252

[02] 136834 | B16470 | L1527 | O53 | Area A

Philip I, Antioch (Tyre/Sidon), Bronze, 100 BCE–100 CE

Weight: 5.22 g
Diameter: 19 mm x 21 mm
Axis: 12
Obv legend: Around, clockwise from seven o'clock: [ΑΥΤΟΚΚΜΙΟΥΛΙΦΙΛΙΠΠΟΣΣΕΒ]
Obv design: Bust of Philip I, r., draped and curiaised;
Rev legend: Around, clockwise from seven o'clock: [ΑΝΤΙΟΧΕΩΝ — ΜΗΤΡΟΚΟΛΩΝ]
Rev design: Apollo standing facing, head, l., holding lyre in l. hand and phiale in extended r. hand, coiled serpent at feet to l. In field, Δ–E/S–C.
Literature: Butcher 2004: 397–98, No 498; *BMC Syria* 534.

[03] 136835 | B16753 | L1529 | H54 | Area A

Philip I, Antioch (Syria), Bronze, Second Issue. 244–249 CE

Weight: 12.41 g
Diameter: 33 mm
Axis: 12
Obv legend: [ΑΥΤ]ΟΚ Κ ΜΙΟΥΦΙΛΙΠΠΟΣ ΣΕΒ
Rev legend: ΑΝΤΙΟΧΕΩΝ - ΜΗΤΡΟΚΟΛΩ
Literature: Butcher 2004: 397, No 498

[04] 136836 | B16754 | L1529 | H54 | Area A

Trajan, Rome, Quadrans. Bronze, 98–117 CE

Weight: 2.25 g
Diameter: 17 mm
Axis: 6
Obv legend: [IMP CAES TRAIAN AVG GERM]
Obv design: Bust of Heracles, diademed, r., with lion-skin on neck.
Rev design: Boar walking r.; In ex.: SC
Literature: Cf. *CRE* III: 226, No 1062; *RIC* II, 702 (S)

[05] 136837 | B16756 | L1529 | H54 | Area A

Philip I, Antioch (Syria), Debased Silver, 249 CE

Weight: 11.85 g
Diameter: 27 mm
Axis: 12
Obv legend: ΑΥΤΟΚ Κ Μ ΙΟΥΛΙ ΦΙΛΙΠΠΟΣ ΣΕΒ
Obv design: Philip I, r., laureate, draped and curiaised, seen from behind.
Rev legend: ΔΗΜΑΡΧ ΕΕ ΟΥΚΙΑΣ ΥΠΙΑΤΟΔ
Rev design: Eagle, l.
Literature: Prieur & Prieur 2000: 65, No 444

[06] 136838 | B16759 | L1529 | H54 | Area A

Severus Alexander, Tyre, Bronze, 222–235 CE

Weight: 10.54 g
Diameter: 25 mm
Axis: 6
Obv legend: IMP GORDIANVS-PIVS FEL [AVG]
Obv design: Bust of Severus Alexander, r., laureate, wearing paludamentum and curaiss.
Rev legend: COL TVR MET (differs from example on BMC Phoen.)
Rev design: Temple of the Phoenician Koinon, seen in perspective, approached by flight of steps; number of columns obscure; below, murex-shell.
Literature: Cf. *BMC Phoen*: 280, No 421 (Reverse type appears under Severus Alexander only)

[07] 136839 | B16797 | L1531 | Area A

Roman provincial, unknown mint, Bronze, 100–299 CE

Weight: 2.40 g
Diameter: 17 mm
Axis: 6
Obv design: Bust, r.
Rev design: Bust of woman, r.
Literature: Cf. Spijkerman 1978: 254–55, No 39 (Cf. Commodus of Philadelphia/Amman)

[08] 136840 | B16772 | L1532 | H54 | Area A

Severus Alexander, Bostra, Bronze, 222–235 CE

Weight: 4.87 g
Diameter: 21 mm
Axis: 6
Obv legend: IMP [CAES M AV B SEV — ALEXANΔER AVG]
Obv design: Bust of Severus Alexander, r., laureate, wearing paludamentum and cuirass, shown from the rear.
Rev legend: COLONIA B — OSTRA
Rev design: Bust of city-goddess, l., draped and turreted; cornucopiae at shoulder.
Literature: Spijkerman 1978: 80–81, No 50

[09] 136841 | B16785 | L1532 | H54 | Area A

Hadrian, (uncertain mint), Bronze, 117–138 CE

Weight: 6.90 g
Diameter: 18 mm x 16 mm
Obv legend: [...]
Obv design: Bust of Hadrian, r. (identification of coin based on portrait)
Rev design: Illegible.

[10] 136842 | B16762 | L1529 | H54 | Area A

Elagabalus, Byblos, Bronze, 218–222 CE

Weight: 11.07 g
Diameter: 28 mm x 21 mm
Axis: 12
Obv legend: [IMPCAISMAR ANTONINVS AV]
Obv design: Bust of Elagabalus, r., laureate, wearing paludamentum and cuirass;
Rev legend: [IE PAC BVBAOV]
Rev design: Temple of six columns containing a figure of Astarte crowned by Nike; of the temple, a central arch (which has traces of shell-pattern) is shown surmounted by an uncertain akroterion (quadriga?), and flanked by wings supported each by three columns.
Literature: *BMC Phoen*: 105, No 50

2001 Season (5 coins)

[01] 116502 | B16317 | L1508 | O53 | Area A

Al-Kamil Muhammad (Ayyubid), Damascus, Bronze, 633 AH (= 1238 CE)

Weight: 4.31 g
Diameter: 21 mm
Obv design: (Arabic)
Rev design: (Arabic)
Literature: Cf. Balog 1980: 169, No 465

[02] 116503 | B16384 | L1515 | O53 | Area A

Alexander Jannaeus, Jerusalem, Bronze, 104–80/79 BCE

Weight: 0.93 g
Diameter: 13 mm
Obv legend: [BA]ΣΙΑ[ΕΩΣ ΑΛΕΞΑΝΔΡΟΥ] (of King Alexander)
Obv design: Anchor surrounded by Greek inscription; around, circle of dots.
Rev legend: [Between rays of star, paleo Hebrew inscription: יהנתן המלך (Yehonatan the King)]
Rev design: Eight-pointed star in diadem.
Literature: *AJC* 1: 119, No Ca; *TJC*: 209–10, Group K

[03] 116504 | B16396 | L1515 | O55 | Area A

Sulaiman I (Ottoman), Egypt, Silver, 1520–1566 CE

Obv design: (Arabic)

[04] no IAA # | (no basket) | L480

Autonomous, Syria (Modern), Brass

Weight: 1.17 g
Diameter: 13 mm x 16 mm

[05] no IAA # | B16281 | L1505 | O53 | Area A

Unidentifiable Coin

Appendix Two: Coins from the 2013 Season

Twenty-nine (29) coins were recovered during the 2013. These are yet to be cleaned and identified, but a preliminary listing is provided here for the sake of completeness.

<i>Date</i>	<i>Basket</i>	<i>Locus</i>	<i>Grid</i>	<i>Area</i>
21/05/13	11311	1169	L60	A South
4/06/13	11350	1171	L60	A South
7/06/13	31060	4005	B68	T
10/06/13	31068	4005	B68	T
11/06/13	31094	4006	B68	T
14/06/13	31108	4006	B68	T
19/06/13	21923	5735	Z28	C
19/06/13	31124	4008	B70	T
20/06/13	11390	1185	M58	A South
21/06/13	21295	5734	C29	C
24/06/13	23611	2263	F59	A West
24/06/13	23612	2262	G58	A West
24/06/13	23613	2263	F59	A West
24/06/13	23614	2263	F59	A West
24/06/13	31144	4007	B69	T
25/06/13	21941	5734	C29	C
25/06/13	23623	2263	F59	A West
26/06/13	23628	2262	G58	A West
26/06/13	23631	2263	F59	A West
27/06/13	11422	1180	J60	A South
27/06/13	21950	5737	Z28	C
27/06/13	23636	2263	F59	A West
27/06/13	23637	2263	F59	A West
27/06/13	23638	2263	F59	A West
27/06/13	23640	2263	F59	A West
27/06/13	23641	2263	F59	A West (not a coin)
27/06/13	31163	4008	B70	T
28/06/13	23647	2262	G58	A West
28/06/13	23649	2263	F59	A West
28/06/13	31170	4007	B69	T

References

- AJC Meshorer, Yaakov. *Ancient Jewish Coinage: I: Persian Period through Hasmoneans; II: Herod the Great through Bar Cochba*. New York, NY: Amphora, 1982. [Now out of date and replaced by JTC.]
- Ariel 2012 Ariel, Donald T., and Jean-Philippe Fontanille. *The Coins of Herod: A Modern Analysis and Die Classification*. Ancient Judaism and Early Christianity 79. Leiden: Brill, 2012.
- Balog 1964 Balog, Paul, *The coinage of the Mamluk sultans of Egypt and Syria*. Numismatic Studies, 12. New York, American Numismatic Society, 1964
- Balog 1980 Balog, Paul, *The coinage of the Ayyubids*. Special publication (Royal Numismatic Society), no. 12. London: Royal Numismatic Society, 1980.
- Barkay 2003 Barkay, Rachel, *The coinage of Nysa-Scythopolis Beth-Shean*. Coprus Nummorum Palaestinenium 5. Jerusalem: Israel Numismatic Society, 2003.
- Berman 1976 Berman, Ariel, *Islamic Coins*. Jerusalem: L. A. Mayer Memorial Institute for Islamic Art, 1976.
- BMCO Poole, Stanley L. *Catalogue of Oriental Coins in the British Museum*. 4 vols. London: British Museum, 1877.
- BMC Palestine Hill, George Francis. *Catalogue of the Greek Coins of Palestine. A Catalogue of the Greek Coins in the British Museum*. London: British Museum, 1914
- BMC Phoen Hill, George Francis. *Catalogue of the Greek Coins of Phoenicia. A Catalogue of the Greek Coins in the British Museum*. London: British Museum, 1910.
- BMC Syria Wroth, Warwick. *Catalogue of the Greek Coins of Galatia, Cappadocia, and Syria. A Catalogue of the Greek Coins in the British Museum*. London: British Museum, 1899.
- Butcher 2004 Kevin Butcher, *Coinage in Roman Syria. Northern Syria, 64 BC – AD 253*. Royal Numismatic Society Special Publication 34. London: Royal Numismatic Society, 2004.
- Carradice & Price 1988 Carradice, Ian, and Martin Price. *Coinage of the Greek World*. London, UK: Seaby, 1988.
- CRE Carson, R. A. G. *Coins of the Roman Empire*. London: Routledge, 1990.
- Davesne 1989 Alain Davesne, *Anatolie antique : fouilles françaises en Turquie : catalogue de l'exposition, Bibliothèque nationale... 1er décembre 1989-16 avril 1990....* Varoa anatlica 4. Paris : [Bibliothèque nationale] ; Istanbul : Institut français d'études anatoliennes, 1989
- Hendin 2010 Hendin, David. *Guide to Biblical Coins*. 5th ed. New York, NY: Amphora, 2010.
- Howgego 1985 Howgego, C. J., *Greek imperial countermarks: Studies in the provincial coinage of the Roman Empire*. Royal Numismatic Society Special publication 17. London: Royal Numismatic Society, 1985.
- Jacobson & Kokkinos 2102 Jacobson, David M., and Nikos Kokkinos, eds. *Judaea and Rome in Coins 65 BCE - 135 CE*, Papers Presented at the International Conference Hosted by Spink, 13-14 September 2010. London: Spink, 2012.
- Jenks 2013 Jenks, Gregory C., "A Roman coin from Bethsaida (Et-tell)." in *A Life in Parables and Poetry: Pedagogue, Poet, Scholar. Essays in honor of Mishael Maswari Caspi*, edited John T. Greene. (forthcoming).
- Kadman 1957 Leo Kadman, *The coins of Caesarea Maritima*. Corpus Nummorum Palaestinenium, 2. Jerusalem : The Universitas-Publ. : [then] Schocken Publ. House Tel-Aviv, 1957

- Kadman 1961 Kadman, Leo. *The Coins of Akko Ptolemais*. Corpus Nummorum Palaestinensium, 1st Series. Publications of the Israel Numismatic Society. Vol. 4, Jerusalem: Schocken, 1961.
- Kindler 1961 Kindler, Arie. *The Coins of Tiberias*. Tiberias: Hamei Tiberia, 1961.
- Kindler 1999 Kindler, Arie. "The Coins of the Tetrarch Philip and Bethsaida." In *Bethsaida: A City by the North Shore of the Sea of Galilee*, edited by Rami Arav and Richard A. Freund 2,245–49. Kirksville, MO: Truman State University Press, 1999.
- Kindler 2009 "Bethsaida Numismatic Survey: Seasons of 1997 through 2000." Chap. 12 In *Bethsaida: A City by the North Shore of the Sea of Galilee*, edited by Rami Arav and Richard A. Freund, 4,252–66. Kirksville, MO: Truman State University Press, 2009.
- Kreitzer 1996 Kreitzer, Larry Joseph. *Striking New Images: Roman Imperial Coinage and the New Testament World*. Journal for the Study of the New Testament Supplement Series 134. Sheffield, UK: Sheffield Academic Press, 1996.
- Lindgren I Lindgren, Henry Clay. *Ancient Bronze Coins of Asia Minor and the Levant from the Lindgren Collection*. San Mateo, CA: Chrysopylon Publications, 1985.
- Lindgren II Lindgren, Henry Clay. *Ancient Greek Bronze Coins: European Mints from the Lindgren Collection*. San Mateo, CA: Chrysopylon Publishers, 1989.
- Lindgren III Lindgren, Henry Clay. *Ancient Greek Bronze Coins from the Lindgren Collection*. San Francisco, CA: Classical Numismatic Group, 1993.
- Lorber PC Lorber, Catharine C. *Coinage of the Ptolemaic Empire* (forthcoming).
- LRBC R. A. G. Carson, P. V. Hill & J. P. C. Kent, *Late Roman Bronze Coinage A.D. 324–498. I: The Bronze Coinage of the House of Constantine A.D. 324–346. II: Bronze Roman Imperial Coinage of the Later Empire A.D. 346–498*. New York, NY: Spink, 1978.
- Meier 1995 Meier, Cecilia. "Appendix to Chapter 1: Breakdown of Coins by Period (until 1993 Season)." In *Bethsaida: A City by the North Shore of the Sea of Galilee*, edited by Rami Arav and Richard A. Freund 1,53–63. Kirksville, MO: Thomas Jefferson University Press, 1995.
- Meshorer, Bijovsky & Fischer-Bossert Meshorer, Yaakov, Gabriela Bijovsky, and Wolfgang Fischer-Bossert, eds. *Coins of the Holy Land: The Abraham and Marian Sofaer Collection at the American Numismatic Society and the Israel Museum*. 2 vols, Ancient Coins in North American Collections 8. New York, NY: American Numismatic Society, 2013.
- Newell 1936 Edward T. Newell, *The Pergamene mint under Philetaerus*. Numismatic Notes and Monographs 76. New York, American Numismatic Society, 1936.
- Pere 1968 Pere, Nuri, *Coins of the Ottoman empire. Istanbul*: 1968.
- Poey D'Avant Fautin Poey D'Avant, *Monnaies Féodales de France*. Paris, 1858; repr. Graz: Druck, 1961
- RIC Mattingly, H., Edward A. Sydenham, and C. H. V. Sutherland. *The Roman Imperial Coinage*. Vol. IV, Part II, London: Spink, 1938.
- TJC Meshorer, Yaakov. *A Treasury of Jewish Coins: From the Persian Period to Bar Kokhba*. Jerusalem: Yad Ben-Zvi Press, 2001.
- Prieur & Prieur 2000 Michel Prieur & Karin Prieur, *The Syro-Phoenician tetradrachms and their fractions from 57 BC to AD 253*. London: Classical Numismatic Group, 2000.
- Rosenberger 1972 Rosenberger, Mayer. *City Coins of Palestine. 1: Aelia, Kapitolina, Akko, Anthedon Antipatris and Ascalon*. Jerusalem, 1972.
- Rosenberger 1977 Rosenberger, Mayer. *City Coins of Palestine. 3: Hippos-Sussita, Neapolis, Nicopolis, Nysa-Scytopolis, Caesarea-Panias, Pelusium, Raphia, Sebaste,*

- Sepphoris-Diocaesarea, Tiberias*. Rosenberger Israel Coin Collection 3. Jerusalem, 1977.
- SC Houghton, Arthur, Catharine Lorber, and Oliver Hoover, eds. *Seleucid Coins. A Comprehensive Catalogue: Part 1: Seleucus I through Antiochus III; Part 2. Seleucus IV through Antiochus XIII*. 4 vols. New York, NY: American Numismatic Society, 2002-2008.
- Sear 1982 Sear, David R. *Greek Imperial Coins and Values*. London: Seaby, 1982.
- SNG Israel Houghton, Arthur, and Arnold Spaer. *The Arnold Spaer Collection of Seleucid Coins*. Sylloge Nummorum Graecorum Israel 1. London: Italo Vecchi, 1998.
- SNG Ptol Kromann, Anne, and Otto Morkholm, eds. *Egypt: The Ptolemies*, Sylloge Nummorum Graecorum: The Royal Collection of Coins and Medals. Danish National Museum. Copenhagen: Munksgaard, 1977.
- Spijkerman 1978 Spijkerman, Augustus. *The Coins of the Decapolis and Provincia Arabia*. Studii Biblici Franciscani Collectio Maior 25. Jerusalem: Franciscan Printing Press, 1978.
- Svoronos Svoronos, J. N. *Ta Nomismata tou Kratous ton Ptolemaion*. Translated by Catharine C. Lorber. Athens 1904.
- Syon 2004 Syon, Danny. *Tyre and Gamla: A Study in the Monetary Influence of Southern Phoenicia on Galilee and the Golan in the Hellenistic and Roman Periods*. PhD dissertation, 2004.
- Vagi 2001 Vagi, David L. *Coinage and History of the Roman Empire. 1: History*. Oxford: Routledge, 2001.